

USING LEXICAL GAMES IN CLASS FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The case study suggested an additional psychological condition for learning words through reading: the importance of a wide and free choice of books. The procedure of choosing and "grading" books mentioned before contributed considerably to the motivation of the children to read the selected book and probably as well to their retention of the content.*

Keywords: *social and emotional development, build language, literacy skills, math concepts.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ ИГР НА УРОКАХ ДЛЯ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. *В ходе исследования было предложено дополнительное психологическое условие изучения слов посредством чтения: важность широкого и свободного выбора книг. Упомянутая выше процедура выбора и «оценки» книг в значительной степени способствовала мотивации детей к чтению выбранной книги и, возможно, также сохранению ими содержания.*

Ключевые слова: *социальное и эмоциональное развитие, построение речи, навыки грамотности, математические понятия.*

The case study indicated that this also brought about a good retention of a number of words occurring in important passages of the books. Finally, it was remarkable that the amount of interest in the subject appeared to prevail over the degree of difficulty of the language. This phenomenon and the importance of a free and wide choice was also found in a study concerning the relations between leisure reading in the mother tongue and reading English by Toussaint-Dekker.

As children see concepts reflected in the world around them, they become enthusiastic and engaged learners. These activities help to foster children's social and emotional development, build language and literacy skills, and develop an understanding of math concepts. You will also find science activities that strengthen children's observation and reasoning skills, music and movement activities that get everyone involved, and group art activities that inspire creativity and cooperation.

Activity 1 ALPHABET TOSS

Materials: Large balls

Choose a letter to begin the game, such as the letter *b*. Stand in a circle and toss a ball to a child, saying a word that begins with the letter *b*, such as the word *bat*. That child then throws the ball to another child and says another word that begins with letter *b*, such as the word *baseball*. Continue around the circle. As each child catches the ball, he or she says a word that begins with the chosen letter. As an alternative, this activity can be done in pairs or in small groups.

To challenge children even more, ask them to name, in order, a word for each letter of the alphabet. For younger children: Invite pairs of children to roll or toss the balls back and forth, emphasizing the *b* sounds in the words *ball* and *bounce*.

Activity 2 A BOWL OF JELLY

Materials: None

Invite children to move like things that begin with the letter *j*. First ask children what words they can think of that begin with the letter *j*. They may say words such as *jelly*, *jack-in-the-box*, *jumping jacks*, or *jaguar*. Then invite children to move like the letter *j*!

Activity 3 MONKEY SHINES

Motor Skills

Materials: None

M is for *monkey*! Invite children to act like monkeys—jump on chairs, hop around, swing, make monkey sounds, and so on. If possible, place mats on the floor for children to bounce on. Then ask children if they can think of other animals that begin with the letter *m* (mouse, moose, mole). Children can act out these animals, as well.

Activity 4 UNDER THE UMBRELLA

Materials: Large umbrella

Parachute or large sheet Parent volunteers can help with this activity. Bring a large umbrella to school and invite children to bring umbrellas from home, as well. Show children how you put up the umbrella and how you stand under the umbrella. Show children how you can hold the umbrella upside down. Stress the sound of the letter *u* as they experiment with the umbrellas. Talk about how an upside-down umbrella looks like the letter *u*. Then ask children and parent volunteers to take hold of the edges of a parachute or large sheet. Together, toss the parachute or sheet up in the air, keeping hold of the edge. Encourage children to run under the “umbrella” and back out again. Continue play by calling out the names of children to run under the “umbrella.”

A quantitative approach of lexical richness and variety can offer a macro-picture on the learner's lexicon. In the lexicometric and stylostatistical literature a variety of measures has been proposed for spelling out the lexical characteristics of a written and spoken text. The lexical variety or richness of a text is usually defined as a function of the number of types (V) in relation to the number of tokens (N). The number of tokens constitutes the text length. For the words used by our informants, a set of 11 lexical measures has been selected originally, mainly based on Menard.

The type/token ratio is by far the most widely used measure. Surveying the literature on child language, Richards concludes that in spite of their popularity type/token ratios have frequently failed to discriminate between children at widely different stages of language development. Type/token ratios yield especially biased results if the texts investigated differ considerably in the number of tokens. As we showed in Breeder, Extra & Van Hout 3 measures of lexical richness turned out to be most promising:

(b) Guiraud's index (V/\sqrt{N} , which in fact is comparable to Carroll's diversity measure $V/\sqrt{2N}$),

(c) The number of types, provided the texts do not differ too much in the number of tokens, and

(d) the Theoretical Vocabulary. This is the expected number of types for a specified number of tokens and it is calculated on the basis of the number of types and tokens found in a concrete text.

For a more thorough discussion of this lexical measure see Breeder et al.

In any lexical study on richness and variety information should be provided about the operationalisation of basic categories such as word tokens, word forms, lemmas or other basic counting units. Operationalisation problems will be not discussed here. More information can be found in Breeder et al.

The steps taken in the operationalisation of the lexical data base can be summarized as follows:

First, concordance lists are made which give the word forms used by the learner in alphabetical order, together with the contexts and the frequency of the word forms. Next the list of word forms is 'cleaned up' by excluding, for instance, false word starts, and is converted into a list of word tokens; a word form is defined as a class of identical word tokens.

Finally the word forms are coded and stored in the form of records in which a fixed number of fields specifies the word form, the word class, the hypothesized learner meaning, the lemma,

the frequency, and the place of occurrence (informant, cycle, encounter, activity). The lemma field contains dictionary entries of the target language.

Excluded from the data base are false word starts, but included are word repeats. They are included because repeats can be viewed as a determining property of spontaneous speech in general and of the spontaneous speech of language learners in particular. Every transcript of an activity has a specific number of different word types. The frequency of a word type is the sum of the frequencies of the word forms belonging to that word type. The total frequency of the word types in a text or the number of tokens is the sum of the frequencies of all word types together.

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